

THE ROLE OF CURRICULUM IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE ASSESSMENT

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Abstract. *The research paper discusses the role of the curriculum in English language assessment. The paper aims to provide extensive information on the purpose, principles, and characteristics of assessment in the curriculum. The paper describes the ways in which assessment is integrated into learning in the English language curriculum, explains the ways in which teachers measure students' language learning, and explains the design techniques for assessment tasks and activities. Research and observations show that information on assessment in higher education curricula is at a very low level and that this information briefly presents standards-based assessments. This situation does not allow both teachers and students to provide detailed information on how to successfully achieve learning outcomes in language skills. Teachers have a superficial understanding of the ways in which learning outcomes are measured and the student-centered assessment approach. As a result, assessment cannot accurately measure students' language competence. To this end, the paper presents a comprehensive strategy for assessment in the English language curriculum and provides an opportunity for teachers to become a useful resource in their future practical activities.*

Keywords: *curriculum, learner-centered assessment, task design, measurement*

Резюме. *В данной исследовательской работе обсуждается роль учебной программы в оценивание уровня владения английским языком. Цель работы — предоставить обширную информацию о целях, принципах и характеристиках оценивание в рамках учебной программы. В работе описываются способы интеграции оценивание в процесс обучения английскому языку, объясняются методы, которыми преподаватели измеряют усвоение языка студентами, а также методы разработки оценочных заданий и мероприятий. Исследования и наблюдения показывают, что информация об оценивание в учебных программах высшего образования находится на очень низком уровне, и эта информация кратко представляет собой оценивание, основанные на стандартах. Такая ситуация не позволяет ни преподавателям, ни студентам предоставлять подробную информацию о том, как успешно достичь результатов обучения в области языковых навыков. Преподаватели имеют поверхностное понимание методов измерения результатов обучения и подхода к оценке, ориентированного на студента. В результате оценивание не может точно измерить языковую компетенцию студентов. В связи с этим в работе представлена комплексная стратегия оценивание в рамках учебной программы по английскому языку и предоставляется возможность преподавателям стать полезным ресурсом в своей будущей практической деятельности.*

Ключевые слова: *учебный план, оценивание, ориентированная на обучающегося, разработка заданий, измерение*

1. Introduction.

1.1. English Language Curriculum and Assessment

The English language evaluation of the curriculum is a significant and intricate process that uses assignments, observations, and standardized tests to assess students' proficiency. It ensures that education is focused on the needs and standards of the students by using formative and summative methods to track progress in speaking, listening, writing, and reading.

The term "curriculum" is derived from an ancient Latin word that means "race course." Over the years, educators have interpreted it in various ways. Curriculum, according to Tanner (1980), is "the planned and guided learning experiences and intended outcomes, formulated through the

systematic reconstruction of knowledge and experiences, under the auspices of the school, for the learner's growth in personal social competence."

The assessment of English in the curriculum is based on appropriate principles. These principles include a detailed explanation of the characteristics and objectives of formative and summative assessment, instructions for teachers on how to provide positive feedback, and rules for preparing tests for assessment.

There are various reasons why assessment is crucial in the curriculum. Teaching and learning might use the qualitative information from assessment findings to decide how to improve programs and/or courses by making adjustments to the curriculum, teaching strategies, course materials, or other areas. Assessment results can offer a strong justification for gaining support for curricular and other changes when incorporated into the planning cycle for curriculum development and evaluation.

1.2. Assessment in the English Language Curriculum

Resnick, L. B., and Resnick, D. P. (1992) explained that *"The English curriculum is a framework document that describes the new content, strategy, and assessment of the subject. These three areas require the implementation of competency-based standards, norms, and assessments that are generally accepted in language teaching"* [7, p.39]. Alderson, J. C., and others prove that assessment in English requires the formation of competencies in accordance with the general learning outcomes of the program [1, p.129]. In this regard, assessment should serve the realization of the standards given as formative (continuous) and summative (final) results. Assessment should be balanced with a good mix of formative (continuous) assessment and summative (end-of-unit) assessment to monitor students' competence in a variety of key skills. In student-centered teaching, modern approaches to English use classroom observation, portfolios, and standardized assessment tests in combination to make determinations about language skills like reading, writing, listening, and speaking.

Bachman, L. F., & Palmer, A. S. (2010), Carless, D. (2007) noted that assessment in the English language curriculum in higher education provides a clear and structured framework for monitoring students' progress in language skills at specific stages. The document also provides benchmarks, tests, and rubrics for assessing English language skills at different levels [2; 4]. It provides a unified view of assessment tools and methods for assessing students' skills. The curriculum also provides teachers and assessors with assessment guidelines, and indirect information is meaningless. In order for the assessment to be more effective, the curriculum also explains the student's abilities at each level, including strengths and weaknesses. In addition, information on areas that need improvement is also provided. The curriculum takes the integration of learning into assessment as a basis and denies that it is a separate area. The place of feedback in the curriculum's description of assessment is a significant field. How feedback is given is extensively explained in the curriculum, and its benefits are explained. The tests are given opportunities to adapt to meet the different needs of students.

2. Learner-centered assessment

Black, P., & William, D. (1998) and Gardner, J. (2012) state that the English Language Curriculum Assessment Guidelines recommend learner-centered, continuous, and competency-based assessment. Student-centered assessment in English language teaching is a strategic approach that is central to the curriculum [3; 5]. Their focus is on formative assessment, monitoring progress with final assignments for final proficiency in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Klenowski, V. (1995) emphasized that in this approach, assessment is viewed not as a mere tool but as a learning experience, prioritizing student development and focusing on the acquisition of competencies [6, p.146]. Students become key participants in the assessment process, and both self-assessment and peer assessment are used to ensure quality in the program.

Assessment is an important part of course design. Well-designed tests ensure that the time your students spend on them is valuable in terms of enhancing their learning and/or providing feedback to them. Student-centered assessment ensures that it provides a relevant indicator of their learning. An assessment strategy in the English language curriculum is a quality factor: a planned approach to

assessing students' language skills, progress, and achievements. It aligns assessment methods with curriculum objectives, teaching methods, and learning outcomes.

3. Tasks and activities design in the English Language Curriculum

The English language curriculum includes assessment tasks and activities based on language proficiency, benchmarks, and levels. This design becomes an effective guide for teachers as an assessment of requirements. Teachers and students can easily understand the ways to achieve the learning outcomes in the curriculum. In addition, it offers ways to prepare tests and tasks according to the level of difficulty for perfect mastery of the teaching topics [2; 5; 6].

Tests and tasks design in the English Language Curriculum" is the process of planning, creating, and organizing assessment activities which measure the achievement of the English language learners. Language competency levels, teaching strategies, and curriculum objectives should all be reflected in these evaluations.

Conclusion

Thus, the role of the curriculum in the effective implementation of assessment in English language teaching is indispensable. This document serves as an orientation for both teachers and students. The curriculum requires the effective organization of student-centered learning based on appropriate principles, integrating it into learning in a systematic way. The teaching process requires the role of quality-based approaches and encourages the use of measurable tasks and activities in English language acquisition.

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